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Using intangible cultural heritage as a reconciliation and development tool – Western Balkan experience

Research-based recommendations for professionals and policymakers

These recommendations are based on a multi-year study of the state of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) safeguarding in the Western Balkansⁱⁱ but consider their broader implications. The Western Balkans, as a “typical” post-conflict region, is a valuable field in which policy professionals can learn how to deal with the issues related to identity politicization while also developing an understanding of how to use social sciences and humanities (SSH) to maintain peace and reconcile communities confronted on identity grounds.

The findings of this research illustrate the considerably different ways in which ICH is currently defined, researched, safeguarded, and managed in Western Balkan contexts, but in all cases there is an open issue of the underrepresentation of minority, shared and contested ICH (a flammable situation in need of an urgent intervention). Compared to typical cooperation processes such as justice, security, energy, or infrastructure, regional cooperation in social development policies is low on the priority lists of political leadership in SEE countries although it has the highest potential to have a tangible and positive impact on people’s everyday lives.ⁱⁱⁱ However, there are important initiatives such as The Council of Ministers of Culture of South-East Europe (CoMoCoSEE, created in 2005)^{iv} established by the Council of Europe and the European Commission. Also, Regional Program for Cultural and Natural Heritage in South-East Europe^v has already proved to be a major platform for joint rehabilitation and the survey of architectural and archaeological, i.e., monumental heritage. ICH safeguarding as a reconciliation tool lags behind, with the 2010-established RCC Task Force on Culture and Society having its activities mainly frozen since 2015,^{vi} with the promising yet slightly forgotten Belgrade and Ohrid Declarations,^{vii} and the Ljubljana Process.^{viii} This noble idea of creating forums that will bring heritage stakeholders together and enable dialogue on sensitive issues is hampered by issues related to their organizational structure, since they gather very high level officials and few heritage scholars and safeguarding practitioners.

Among the numerous identified political and security issues related to ICH safeguarding, the most important are those concerning a) the position of ethnic and religious minorities and b) the position of social sciences and humanities, institutions, and individual researchers. A solution to the problem of grounding political extremism in ideological fundamentalism, often aided by humanities scholarships, should be sought concurrently in both domains.

The promotion and facilitation of dialogue in building an inclusive approach to ICH safeguarding should be based on the opening of existing state safeguarding networks for the permanent advisory role of representatives of national minorities and ethnic communities, as key *actors missing from* this process. Such a role for minority representatives can be realized through both permanent program and periodic project-based activities. Also, it can be realized within separate cultural institutions of national importance that have yet to be established. The high level of existing cooperation between academic, research, and museum institutions in the system of cultural heritage safeguarding, together with the positive results of fieldwork among ethnologists working as expert-bureaucrats on the possibility of opening the safeguarding

systems to minority communities, suggest that there is a will to perform this important task competently and dedicatedly.

With this general goal, it is necessary to focus on those elements of the ICH that form the perceived core of the cultural identities of national minorities and ethnic communities in order to achieve the following specific results:

- (a) the opening of national cultural policies for the safeguarding of minority identities;
- (b) enriching and strengthening the institutional infrastructure in the field of ICH safeguarding, as well as
- (c) giving impetus to new forms of the cultural expression of minorities (including those directly related to economic change, such as sustainable community development through tourism, entrepreneurship advancement, increased participation of minorities, women, and youth in political life, and the like).

The politicization, and especially the internationalization of the new variant of the “minority issue” in the form of culturalized bilateral conditionality^{ix}, in the domain of (the absence of) the safeguarding of minority cultural heritage should be prevented. It is advisable to follow the regional South-East European (SEE) and national approach at the same time — to safeguard the elements of the minority cultural heritage in the regions and through the national networks, so that safeguarding from the very beginning has both a minority-specific and national character in all respective states.

The proposed change in cultural policies relating to minorities, aimed at complementing, not immediately replacing, many of the existing mechanisms, envisages a series of interrelated activities aimed at (a) developing approaches to the safeguarding of ICH at the political and administrative level in multiethnic contexts as a standard activity incorporated in annual programs; and (b) raising awareness of inclusive, rather than conflicting, perceptions of identity issues, with the safeguarding of ICH as a bridge of cooperation between state and minority stakeholders. In addition, although no less important, the gradual replacement of existing, conflict-sensitive forms of the manifestation of minority identities within predominantly segregative multicultural identity politics, with this safer framework for the safeguarding of ICH, has an international component. The ICH is inextricably linked to the safeguarding of human and minority rights and forms the very core of the enjoyment of the right to cultural identity of minority groups. Its safeguarding is an essential element of cooperation and the harmonization of relations that the international community encourages among governments in the Western Balkans. Therefore, the return of dignity to minority communities in their efforts to make the general population aware of the values of their own culture and identity through multicultural recognition policies should be continued and supplemented. Then, it should be gradually redirected to activities that are purposefully moved from the public arena and framed both by ratified international conventions and domestic legislation. UNESCO’s global program for the preservation of intangible culture undoubtedly opens up new possibilities in that regard.

To this end, significant support is needed for the adaptation and implementation of instruments developed by UNESCO in cooperation with national governments in the field of the safeguarding of cultural heritage, especially the ICH of national minorities and ethnic groups. The support of all relevant sectors for existing programs and projects, as well as for the development of future ones, would effectively contribute to the inclusion of as many members of

minority communities as possible in the state ICH safeguarding system. In this regard, in the future remodeling of ICH safeguarding networks, special attention should be paid to the accompanying Operational Directives to the 2003 Convention,^x which emphasize the obligation of Member States to include underrepresented groups in the safeguarding system. It is necessary to help the population, state, and local self-government institutions to continue, expand, and deepen the process of incorporating minority identities into the official state system by combining the fulfillment of international obligations and providing support to minority voices at the national, regional, and local levels.

The launch of cultural racism prevention programs should be actively supported, especially in the context of the prolonged economic crisis, political responses to it in the form of austerity measures, the ubiquitous “end of multiculturalism” style of government, most recent COVID-19 related social dismay and the “world war” discourse spanning through the region as a consequence of the aggression on Ukraine. Both in the education curriculum and in long-term research plans within institutions, faculties, institutes, museums and other cultural institutions, as well as those media in which cultural and educational programs have not yet been extinguished. Despite the economic crisis, it is necessary to allocate funds in both national and regional budgets to support such teaching, research, and media programs.

In order to promote cultural heritage, as well as education and employment — bearing in mind that the safeguarding of cultural heritage provides significant opportunities in this regard — it is necessary to create conditions for a number of members of national minorities and ethnic groups to be targeted in ICH safeguarding programs in the capacity of “minority coordinators” or alike. This could be introduced as a separate cultural institution within state administrations under the auspices of UNESCO analogous to the institution of the ombudsman, which is not unfamiliar to the region’s legislatures. The prospective engagement of these “missing stakeholders” should not be confined to periodic, project-based, small-goal activities. It should, instead, be organized within state-governed, regionally or municipally co-funded, stable and respected cultural institutions, such as existing regional museums, libraries, and cultural centers, with close ties to the academic sector. In other words, fieldwork paradoxically pointed to the need of “moving” the issue from civil society and the closed professional arenas to which it has been confined so far, to more established institutions that enjoy wide social authority. I would also recommend supporting projects aimed at selecting and training minority ICH coordinators. In their selection and training, it is wise to cooperate actively with legitimate representatives of minority communities, in order to prevent conflicts over the selection and use of heritage within the communities themselves, but also to include “minorities within minorities” where there are conflicts over representation and leadership not between a community and the state, but within it.

It is especially important to support cross-sectoral cooperation projects uniting the activities of the academic sector, non-governmental sector, and state administration and regional self-government, in efforts to prevent identity-based social conflicts. The main instrument for unifying these activities can be the ICH Inclusive Safeguarding Network (as currently exemplified by ICH SEE Expert Network)^{xi} at both national and regional levels. In this regard, it is worth considering the establishment of an independent regulatory body, such as an agency, which would be free from everyday political burdens and deserve broad legitimacy. Such an agency, regional in its reach (and tied to some of the ongoing policy initiatives that all the countries accept), should then be entrusted with initiating, evaluating, and implementing the results of the detection, selection, analysis, safeguarding, and promotion of elements of the minority ICH. Special attention should be paid to the adaptation of the ICH network of inclusive

safeguarding in highly multicultural environments — provinces/regions or cities. Emphasis should be placed on the participation of representatives of minority communities in the organization and implementation of a wide range of consultative forums on the selection of representative elements of their heritage — forums, seminars, workshops, conferences. This includes the possibility of establishing a Standing Conference on Cultural Heritage that would complement existing forums such as The Council of Ministers of Culture of South-East Europe (CoMoSEE).

The establishment of a National Council for Cultural Heritage in each country under review would significantly contribute to the professionalization and bureaucratization of cultural heritage safeguarding. Safeguarding should not be left exclusively to the project form, based on the enthusiasm, commitment, and expertise of individual university faculties and departments, institute centers, or research groups, learned societies, and often individuals. It should be carried out in an organized and continuous manner, in cooperation with the existing competent state, provincial, city, and regional authorities, as well as with those institutions whose establishment is proposed here. In this sense, it should be possible to programmatically establish budgetary co-financing of those civil society programs that are aimed at studying and preserving cultural heritage, in accordance with the criteria and standards that would be taken care of by the competent body, i.e., the National Council.

Guidelines and recommendations to the academic community stand out as particularly important. ICH research should be intensified in existing academic research organizations. The implementation of the UNESCO conventions and their accompanying operational directives implies the launch of new study programs dedicated to cultural heritage and the ICH specifically, with the introduction of new subjects or subject areas within existing study programs. These curricular changes could be accompanied by the establishment of specific organizational units (departments, seminars, etc.) within existing universities, faculties, departments, divisions, and alike.

Within research and higher education policy, special attention should be paid to the development of applied humanities. Existing efforts to apply the social sciences to the benefit of social needs and the needs of the economy should be supplemented by programs for the application of humanities, with special emphasis on the safeguarding of cultural heritage. When modeling academic policy, we must start with the application of the ratified conventions and operational guidelines of UNESCO and other supranational bodies. They *include in cultural heritage not only art, literature and folklore, but also the academic heritage of a given society*, which is frequently regarded as a group effort rather than an individual effort by each and every scholar. We should be mindful of the fact that missing stakeholders are not only representatives of minority communities, but also all those SSH scholars and practitioners engaged in the exploration, interpretation, and critique of heritagization processes.

Cultural identities based on ethnicity and religion have become distressingly “weaponized” throughout the former Yugoslavia since the 1980s. Following the turmoil of recent years, we face a renewed need for the urgent de-weaponization of cultural identities. Previous research clearly shows that de-weaponization is not feasible through mainstream academic deconstructionist notions that deny the reality of collective identification based on ethnicity and/or religion, and form the dominant approach in the critical social sciences and

humanities, particularly in anthropology. Communities throughout the region, and especially minority communities, feel that their underrepresentation in national ICH registers is just another wave of identity suppression. Sentiments of suppression by rule lead to self-exclusion, segregation by the authorities, and finally to collective identity-based fundamentalism. These are conditions conducive to radicalism and violent extremism. All this is a whole galaxy far, far away from the stabilization agenda pursued by the international community. And there are both newer and broader consequences. It is still too early to assess the ICH consequences of the Ukrainian war, but it is clear that the pan-Slavic identity continuum is both a boon and a risk when it comes to the reweaponization of identities in the Western Balkans. Finally, the raging conflict between Israel and Hamas shows the potential to revive the pan-Arab identity and erase years of efforts in the Israeli-Palestinian dialogue. This is likely to make the strategy of localized identity management in the broader region of the Eastern Mediterranean, the Middle East, and North Africa much difficult.

These findings support the enhancement of existing levels of inter-sectoral cooperation by various institutions and organizations (professional, academic, political, administrative, and civil society organizations [CSOs]) through a combined incentives-learning model, especially when it comes to integrating minority representatives into the Network for Safeguarding ICH in the Western Balkans in order to facilitate intercultural dialogue and reinforce its legitimacy. Promoting and facilitating this dialogical modification of the existing ICH safeguarding network could be based on its programmatic opening to minority representatives, either through formal engagement (for example, by instituting “Standing Minority Representative/s”) as civil servant/s or by introducing regional coordinators of minority origin/experienced researchers knowledgeable in particular minority heritages (and respected by the relevant communities).

The establishment of distinct ICH departments, with ethnologists and allied experts of minority origin (or those professionally interested in minority ICH) in post, in all regional museums throughout the country, is recommended. That would most likely support the sustainable infrastructure for an inclusive ICH safeguarding network.

A minority heritage ombudsman — an unbiased third party, selected by the Coordination of National Minorities or some similar reputable representative body, should be established in countries of the region in order to resolve externally disputes over concrete heritage elements or some heritagization practice (for instance, in cases of perceived exclusion, omission, appropriation, etc.).

An important step toward raising respect for the cultural rights of minorities on national agendas would be to establish an institution specifically designed for the research and safeguarding of minority and contested heritage on the WB or even SEE level. Its form — whether an agency, office, or policy institute, with a decentralized structure (in order for its departments to cover all territorially dispersed minorities), or a combined academic/professional institution, also with territorial departments (and able to conduct research and teaching, alongside the administration of minority heritage) — is not a technical issue but a legitimizing prerequisite. It should act relatively independently of central governments, in order to further prevent heritage debates becoming an issue in day-to-day politics. It is clear that implementing this recommendation will be the most challenging, considering that control over cultural institutions is one of the main tools for exercising interpretative sovereignty.

Independent pressure groups should be established at national levels to lobby for passing laws on ICH and bylaws specific to its safeguarding. Those groups would consist of reputable individuals and representatives of the national councils of minorities, academic and cultural

institutions, professional associations, and prominent politically active NGOs. Under these laws, national councils and corresponding agencies specializing in ICH should be established, with executive powers conferred on them. This should be accompanied by the horizontal harmonization of rules and regulations, as the existing framework is untidy.

The further coordination and enhanced cooperation of existing national minorities' councils, emphasizing the OSCE and Council of Europe activities that have already commenced in that regard, is also highly recommendable. This strategy is crucial given that bilateral EU conditionality has been intertwined with the perceived lack of minority cultural heritage safeguarding and educational needs deprivation. UNESCO's support for prevention in this regard is highly recommended, especially considering the diversity regional institutions (in terms of both character and scope) on other continents..

Minority heritage should not be left solely to devoted individuals or expert groups, or enacted through occasional projects aimed at the research of some specific heritage element or the training of selected groups; it should be complemented by stable budgetary placements. As this is quite complicated, due to the fact that national minority councils and similar bodies are already allocated resources for exercising cultural autonomy, minority heritage safeguarding should be linked with the safeguarding of the cultural heritage at the national level in order for it not to be treated as occasional, but as a regular, legitimate, and — which is most important - *bureaucratized* activity.

Since ICH safeguarding opens up new economic possibilities, especially to individuals and families who accept the responsibility of becoming “heritage bearers,” the inclusion of a certain number of minority communities' members (preferably by quota, in order not to compromise the system at the very start of its implementation) in chambers of commerce at state, regional, and local levels is recommended. This economic aspect of heritage need not be seen as shameful commercialization, but as an important opportunity, especially in economically deprived regions. However, implementers should be mindful of intra-cultural rifts that economic opportunities may cause, and seek informed advice as they proceed. As this is often not the case, ethnological/applied anthropological advice should be provided for in the relevant documents.

Segregative multicultural policies that result in an “insularity effect” should be gradually abandoned in favor of intercultural registers, preferably at the regional level. Inclusive intercultural ICH registers would more likely reflect the multicultural nature of both statistical and self-perceived regions, complementary with the central national registers that would probably remain dominated by majority/common heritage elements in the future. However, existing multicultural minority-oriented cultural programs should not be abandoned, as swift and unprepared change to a solely intercultural approach would be likely to cause unrest and be counterproductive.

As ICH safeguarding is inextricably tied to notions and perceptions of human and minority rights, a community's dignity, and self-/mutual recognition, its inclusive transformation would directly achieve goals suggested for the Western Balkans by the international community. However, the fact that the existing legal framework is not harmonized should not be seen solely as an obstacle. On the contrary, the scarcity of legal instruments at national levels opens possibilities for the direct institutional implementation of declarations, conventions, decisions, and recommendations by UNESCO, the CoE, OSCE, and other relevant international organizations. Although perfectly harmonized legislation would be an asset and would be an ideal, an approach focused on means-as-ends may be more conducive to the fulfilment of short- to mid-term goals.

Those who are dissatisfied with the outcome of the disintegration of Yugoslavia, and the fact that many of its former federal units are inhabited by Serbs whose heritage the Republic of Serbia has no authority to safeguard, not only challenge the international order of cultural heritage safeguarding, but also reduce the possibility of Serbian heritage safeguarding. It is as if, in this type of criticism, the “if we cannot safeguard it, we will not allow others to do so” style of argument prevails; as if, by opposing the prospect of someone else safeguarding certain heritage, we renounce it forever, at least when it comes to the people for whom it is alive and important. In this way, we turn heritage into an abstract phenomenon that is lost, disputed, destroyed (depending on the level of passion). And it is in this way that we exclude Serb minority communities in other former federal units from international heritage safeguarding mechanisms. This conclusion might be indicative for policies that should be applied for many minorities worldwide.

A combined incentives-learning approach should also be applied in reforming the academic sector, as the value of ICH for security and identity studies should not be left to individual initiatives. Thorough reform of the research evaluation system and pay grade scale in the research sector should include policy-oriented research, especially in the humanities (where it is quite rare). This is important because currently knowledge-to-policy academic work is unvalued. Scholars in public universities and research institutions are reviewed for promotions, salaries, and overall academic standing according to certain “points” defined by rules and regulations that do not recognize knowledge-to-policy publications. This reflects a contradiction between the research assessment indicators and proclaimed strategic goals.

While the “value” of research results is measured by their internationalization, the regulatory framework stresses their social utility at national/regional/local levels. In this way, the current evaluation system of the SSH prevents their societal impact. What should be considered in prospective regulatory reform and not confined to a traditional view of academic work is an approach advocated by UNESCO and the CoE, which considers SSH not only as the research *of*, but as having an integral part *in* the cultural heritage of a nation/society/community. This is not just some local social issue or fringe problem in evaluation studies. It is directly relevant for centering identity research and safeguarding in peace, reconciliation and development efforts by the international community worldwide. Further research on the relationship between research evaluation and the societal impact of SSH throughout the Western Balkans would assist the international community as well, and is highly recommended. The same type of research that connects politics of knowledge to identity politics should be initiated in other post-conflict regions.

The issue of the legitimacy of social and political reforms is reported as perhaps the most relevant to informants coming from outside capital cities and major cultural centers (or from underrepresented disciplines). They underline that regulation in sectors of culture and the media, as well as in sectors of research and higher education, have been constantly imposed in a totalitarian manner by bodies (such as national councils, academic councils, working groups and committees). Imposed regulations are not balanced in terms of disciplines, regions, gender, and ethnicity. On ethnicity, research conducted in the Sandžak region clearly shows double exclusion or a “minority within minority” position of Bosniak intellectuals in Serbia or Serbian intellectuals in Montenegro, who felt doubly excluded from the regulatory processes (both in

terms of their professional affiliation as social scientists/humanities scholars, and their ethnocultural identity). The diversification of participation in education, science, and culture related policymaking is recommended, either by introducing a model based on predefined quotas for minorities and geographical regions, or by introducing regional bodies with delegated duties to culturally and socially contextualize what is considered SSH-quality output. Informants belonging to underrepresented disciplines, regions, genders, and ethnicities all concur that excellence in SSH research should be sought for in its relevance. Therefore, introducing regional research assessment panels to valorize the impact of directed SSH research outputs is recommended.

Due to the lack of financial resources and the prolonged economic crisis, talented young pupils throughout the region are being systematically oriented away from studying the arts and humanities (such as ethnology, history of art or archaeology) or less applicable social sciences (such as sociology). This is not a purely academic issue, because in just a generation and a half, most minority populations will likely be left without the human resources capable of channeling debates in core collective identity-related issues such as history, culture or language, except clergy or party politics ethno-entrepreneurs. Consequently, it is likely that the political instrumentalization of identity-related issues and identity-based conflicts would again be hijacked (as in the 1990s). Therefore, the prospect of minority identity politics would be either linked to radicalization or to assimilation (neither of which is an outcome expected by the international development instruments and especially by UNESCO). Further-on, this means that minority communities would lack the capacity to negotiate sensitive identity-related issues and be more prone to politically adventurous interpretations of heritage (and the lack of its safeguarding). In that regard, preventive work is needed to foresee the cultural and educational needs of smaller/dispersed minority communities in particular, and reorient school/academic curricula. The allocation of resources toward such a goal is a must.

Applied humanities type research and teaching should be introduced and facilitated, as many of these disciplines hold a wealth of knowledge on historical and cultural heritage. The existing policy pressure for socio-cultural research to have social impact should be scrutinized. Disciplines like ethnology/anthropology, history, archaeology, the history of art, and language and literature studies should be directed with more focus and enthusiasm. Both project-based incentives for younger researchers (especially those of minority origin or those coming from majority but studying minority issues), and the institution-based funding of research groups, departments, or institutes should be strategically introduced into policy frameworks.^{xii}

These conclusions and resulting recommendations could be developed into a set of guidelines and action plans, through joint research activities by individuals, research groups, and institutions. For instance, by colleagues who have already helped realize this research and proved cooperation is viable even regarding the most sensitive issues. Identity stakeholders need to be reassured that UNESCO-based cultural heritage safeguarding will not become yet another instrument for their marginalization. Instead, they should be motivated to participate in acknowledging their own significant cultural practices. If carefully balanced by adding upstanding minority representatives, the ICH safeguarding system could prove to be a powerful instrument for promoting intercultural dialogue and sustaining existing peace efforts. When proven useful, an inclusive ICH registry might be applied to comparatively relevant contexts, both regionally and globally, making policy interventions of the knowledge-to-policy kind a channel through which cultural heritage could be acknowledged for its peacekeeping potential worldwide.

Reconcile with the Reconciliation

The international community's dominant approach to the fundamental themes of our research and teaching is the use of cultural heritage safeguarding in post-conflict stabilization and development programs. Instead of opposing it from either anti-essentialist or nationalist positions, we can recognize it, apply it and use it to improve the status of SSH, and of anthropology in particular, in the societies we live in, research or teach about. Objectively degrading the position of the SSH globally does not have to be corrected by theoretical anti-realist exclusivism or nationalistic outburst, as has been the case for the past few decades. Instead, we have access to international post-conflict stabilization processes, in which the basic common research theme of our many disciplines — cultural heritage, is treated as an instrument of first-class importance. Considering how we can contribute to the global peacetime post-conflict stabilization project, applying existing knowledge and new research, can help us understand and demonstrate the reasons for and meaning of the continued existence of our academic field to heritage bearers, the rest of the academic community, or political decision makers. In institutions as in everyday life, the trick is to stay analytical and competently advise but not to sound grumpy or arrogant at the same time. Today, heritage is between two fires — on the one hand it is the basic instrument of identity politics, and on the other it is the target of lively academic disputes. Ethnoprofiteers seem to be beating the drums of war again, with a stick made mostly of intangible cultural heritage, while the academic community responds sharply, pointing to heritage safeguarding as a massive abuse of international mechanisms for purposes contrary to the conventions. The global abuse of the authority of UNESCO or the Council of Europe, which anthropologists and related critical researchers of heritage pointed out more than a decade ago, has knocked on our door. Are joining the abusers or disgust with kitsch the only options we have?

Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), defined by the UNESCO Convention of the same name, represents the very core of ethnoculturally defined identity — a set of symbols, beliefs, rituals and knowledge that communities, and even entire nations, perceive as key markers of identity and continuity, passed down from generation to generation and is constantly rethought in interaction with the environment, other communities, the state, companies, civil society, and the like. Research around the globe shows that communities have one thing in common — they seek to make the ICH, despite its apparently constructed character, unchanging and enduring, an objective feature of cultural identity and historical continuity. Therefore, they try to maintain control over the research, safeguarding or promotion of their own heritage as much as possible. To do so, they entrust heritage to individuals, institutions, or entire scientific disciplines (such as ethnology) that aim to make it real, authentic, and otherwise immutable, even when there is an awareness that they do so only by convention and out of interest.

Precisely because of the capability to represent identity, and on the basis of it to define belonging or non-belonging to a certain group, or even to the whole nation, ICH is the main point of contention in multiethnic countries and regions. As in the Western Balkans, conflicts in many other regions, even when it is clear that they erupt for political or economic reasons, are explained by identity arguments — someone disputes or appropriates someone's heritage, which

is usually considered a reason for intolerance, conflict or war. It is clear that ICH is extremely susceptible to political instrumentalization, especially in sensitive contexts of minority-majority relations, so the safeguarding of heritage, or its absence, is seen not only as an academic-professional or political-economic issue, but also one of security.

After recognizing the importance of cultural heritage in provoking conflicts, including wars, the international community has in recent decades tried to transform it into an instrument for ending those same identity-based conflicts. Establishing peace and reconciliation, developing a sense of unity between the conflicting parties, starting a dialogue, are all functions that are attributed to cultural heritage in post-conflict societies, as a rule multiethnic. The most important international organizations are leading in this instrumental understanding of heritage: the United Nations (especially UNESCO and the Development Program), the OSCE, the European Union, the Council of Europe, NATO, the World Bank, the Stability Pact for Southeast Europe, among others. In their work, they place special emphasis on the principles of the importance of cultural heritage for society and the importance of social networks for building and maintaining peace in post-traumatic contexts. In this understanding, heritage is safeguarded primarily with the aid of rose-tinted spectacles, in light of the role it could play in ending existing conflicts, or preventing them in the future.

The integration of ICH into high politics culminated in the adoption of three conventions: the *Council of Europe Framework Convention on the Importance of Cultural Heritage for Society*, the *UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage* and the *UNESCO Convention on the Safeguarding and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions*. Like in many other regions, the implementation of these conventions in the Western Balkans began optimistically, with the idea of contributing to treating identity as an instrument of peace and development and not disintegration and war. However, it showed many weaknesses, neglecting the power of heritage to divide and provoke. Let's call this approach "Heritage for Peace, Reconciliation and Development". What is especially relevant for this discussion is the fact that in these conventions priority is given to the basic subject of our study — intangible aspects of culture. This is a relative novelty, bearing in mind that heritage in the peacetime key is used mainly in conflict-ravaged states within whose territory exists a monumental heritage of significant importance to humanity. In such situations, heritage is explored, promoted, and safeguarded as a motivational mechanism for both citizens and international actors to commit to achieving or preserving peace (as a platform of dialogue, as a place of promise or oath, and in other ways) using the power of cultural heritage to provoke pride or fear, but also to indicate paths to economic recovery (for example through tourism).

Among the numerous political efforts to put cultural heritage at the service of reconciliation and development, the following stand out:

1. *Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the 2018 UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (Guidelines)*;^{xiii}
2. *Council of Europe European Cultural Heritage Strategy for the 21st Century from 2017 onwards (CoE Strategy 21)*;^{xiv}
3. Key OSCE documents linking identity and security;^{xv} and
4. Use of cultural heritage in World Bank programs.^{xvi}

The UNESCO Guidelines aim to fully involve communities, NGOs and other non-administrative actors in the safeguarding process. They also contain criteria and define

procedures for multinational, serial or joint nominations of ICH elements and encourage the participation of experts and research institutions in the implementation of the Convention. Changes of Guidelines since 2008 acknowledge some of the academic critiques presented in the meantime, especially those aimed at the exclusion of those without power from the heritagization processes (such as, as a rule, ethno-confessional minorities). Their last chapter “The Preservation of Intangible Cultural Heritage and Sustainable Development at the National Level” includes a final subchapter, “Intangible Cultural Heritage and Peace,” which emphasizes the importance of ICH for social cohesion, conflict prevention and resolution, peace restoration, with “[a]chieving lasting peace as a goal.” The Guidelines are closely linked to the *UNESCO Guide to the Provision of Advisory Services*, which states that “the general role of States Parties and other actors in the safeguarding of ICHs (such as researchers and NGOs) is to assist communities in providing concrete practical assistance in preserving an element or contributing to more general measures that create an environment that allows for safeguarding” (page 4).

CoE *Strategy 21* calls on policy makers, stakeholders, and citizens to work together to address societal, developmental, and knowledge challenges. Societal challenges include, but are not limited to: living in peace; preserving collective memory; promoting participatory governance; promoting inclusive heritage. The last and most important includes several tasks that are directly relevant to the knowledge-to-policy aspects of this research: “S1 — Encouraging the involvement of citizens and local authorities to capitalize on their everyday heritage” (which is aimed at the cooperation of citizens with local authorities and associations in the process of identification, interpretation, study, and heritage promotion); “S3 — Using heritage to identify and transmit the core values of Europe and European society” (to help citizens see beyond specific national, regional, or local characteristics in order to develop a common sense of belonging and history in line with core European values); “S4 — Promotion of heritage as a meeting place and a means of intercultural dialogue, peace, and tolerance”; “S5 — Assessment of existing practices and procedures for citizen participation”; “S9 — Support for intergenerational and intercultural projects for the promotion of heritage, among other tasks aimed at economic development.” The “development challenge” also applies to research and not only to heritage safeguarding. The “knowledge challenge” explicitly requires closer cross-sectoral cooperation and the inclusion of research and educational practices in the preservation of socially relevant heritage, and includes “[s]upport, strengthening and promoting intergovernmental cooperation” and “[e]ncouraging heritage research.” This also may be considered an opportunity to develop a solution within differentiated EU integration framework.^{xvii} Such a solution could contribute to the integration of policies by UNESCO and the Council of Europe, with the activities of the Union itself and its partners, as well as partners of individual states, such as large international organizations in which not all countries are members.

As a predominantly security-oriented organization, the OSCE considers cultural identity to be one of the focuses of its activities, as the sense of endangered collective identity is considered a major driver of violence, racism, xenophobia, and extremist behavior in general. The 1989 Vienna Concluding Document calls on participating States to ensure that minorities in their territory can maintain and develop their culture in all its aspects, including language, literature, and religion; and are able to preserve their cultural and historical monuments and objects (OSCE, Concluding Document of the Vienna Meeting). The Copenhagen Documents deepen the emphasis on the importance of collective/cultural rights, stating that the recognizing the rights of persons belonging to national minorities as part of

universally recognized human rights is “an essential factor for peace, justice, stability, and democracy in the participating States” (30), which agree to “undertake to establish and maintain unhindered contacts within their country States with which they share a common ethnic or national origin, cultural heritage or religious beliefs” (32.4) and that “[i]n the context of teaching history and culture in educational institutions, they take into account the history and culture of national minorities” (34).

Finally, the World Bank’s doctrine of conflict management through development policy, set out a quarter of a century ago, contains general standards, among which the most relevant for us are: “ESS8: Cultural Heritage” which defines heritage based on its social functions: “ESS8 recognizes that cultural heritage provides continuity between past, present, and future in tangible and intangible forms. People identify with cultural heritage as a reflection and expression of their values, beliefs, knowledge, and traditions that are constantly evolving. Cultural heritage, in many manifestations, is important as a source of valuable scientific and historical information, as an economic and social good for development and as an integral part of the cultural identity and practice of the people.” ESS8 also defines stakeholder involvement: “Stakeholders include, as appropriate: (a) the parties involved in the project, including individuals and communities in the country who use or have used the cultural heritage in living memory; and (b) other stakeholders, which may include national or local regulatory bodies entrusted with the safeguarding of cultural heritage and non-governmental organizations and cultural heritage experts, including national and international cultural heritage organizations.

“Heritage for Peace, Reconciliation and Development” is a paradigm that has shown some positive effects in the Western Balkans, although it has opened up a number of issues, such as the debate on the ethnic or state attribution of heritage, which supplies the majority of examples of new conflicts started by the instrument set up in order to prevent them (like a contraindicated drug). Today, we are witnessing the repoliticization of heritage and the rearmament of identity, a process in which not only nationalistic sermons but also international conventions, whose goal was precisely to prevent a return to the 1990s, are used.

The dominant approach of anthropology and critical heritage studies to heritage itself and its safeguarding is deconstructivist and anti-realist. Heritage is seen as a framework for mythologizing the past of the dominant (ethnic, religious, class, etc.) group, which includes and, more importantly, excludes those who gain or do not gain certain political or economic rights on the basis of (non)belonging. That is exactly why the conventions mentioned above, especially the most important — the 2003 UNESCO Convention — were welcomed with apprehension in the theoretically uncompromising sector of the academic community. Across the planet, interesting and not only didactically, but also politically and ethically important controversies have begun over the role of states against society in heritage safeguarding; the position of minorities; and the role of academia and market mechanisms in this process. Anthropology and critical heritage studies are at the forefront of criticism, which consistently points to the negative aspects of treating the analytical concept as a real phenomenon (similar to the controversy over the concept of culture during previous decades). Analyses of this type indicate that the process of the selection of heritage to be safeguarded is a political act, and that all of us who map, research, safeguard, and promote heritage not only make it available, but through that process shape, design, or literally create it. The process of heritage safeguarding implies the (intentional or

spontaneous) homogenization of human populations, both majority and minority, with frequent opposition from members of both the majority and minority, on whom those customs and beliefs are imposed. This phenomenon is especially dangerous in societies where there is a legacy of neglecting and even erasing one's heritage. Many authors point to the paradoxical aspect of this process, which sometimes represents legal assimilation legitimized by state and international legal and political instruments.

Furthermore, and no less importantly, researchers point out that safeguarding practices standardize heritage for one's benefit, not only in political or economic terms, but also in terms of identity in the narrower sense, many communities and individuals are left outside the framework of the tradition to be followed. By symbolically repressing individuals and groups who do not share the dominant view of the history, tradition, and heritage of the group that took over the heritagization process, the process itself provides a framework to suppress individual differences, and the ability of individuals and groups to create, design, change, or reject cultural practices that have been declared standard. Anthropological research indicates a planned, conscious use of heritage safeguarding mechanisms, which were initially aimed at contributing to the recognition of cultural diversity, for cultural homogenization and assimilation. Instead of contributing to the diversity of cultural expressions, heritage safeguarding is often used to eliminate undesirable cultural practices by creating the illusion of reality and authenticity.

Unlike theoretical anti-realist critiques of heritage safeguarding, characteristic of a "purely" academic response to conservation challenges, another type of critique of the very notion of cultural heritage, as used in international post-conflict stabilization projects, is characteristic of the national humanities and is predominantly nationalistic. It is colored by identity exclusivism and manifested in theories of interpretive sovereignty, which reach their peak in the simultaneous struggle for the special status of national sciences and the privileged status of national culture.

The evaluation of research, researchers themselves, and institutions they work in, as well as the use of academic knowledge, has been under fierce debate for decades. Many of us point out, sometimes at the cost of difficulties caused by opposition to the establishment with judicial epilogues, the bias of evaluation criteria, uneven funding and the symbolic humiliation of SSH, and "identity sciences" in particular, both in academic institutions and in institutions that regulate and manage the academic sector, as well as in the general public. Our highlighting of the fact that the results of our work are systematically disqualified as unimportant, that we are outvoted in a majoritarian style in bodies that decide on evaluation criteria and other relevant issues of academic work, and that the diversity of our academic field is neglected, is systematically ignored. A tradition of neglect on social and cultural issues, and especially on identity issues, has been established worldwide. We agree on that, whether we criticize the safeguarding of heritage as too much or too little nationally colored.

In a recent qualitative study conducted among SSH researchers and professors, I examined the connection between the lack of involvement of our academic field, and especially its humanities wing, with the problem of the lack of the meaningful and fair evaluation of our research. According to the prevailing attitude among colleagues, our disciplines will not make a significant contribution to reform processes, especially the implementation of stabilization mechanisms, unless their status in the wider academic field changes. The status of SSH has proven to be a major obstacle to the inclusion of most of our disciplines in the reform processes in which they are nominally invited to participate.

Among the numerous findings that, taken together, show exceptional commitment of colleagues from our academic field to solving the problem of underrepresentation which connects historical injustices to identity-based communities and disciplines that research them one stands out. It is the need for fair evaluation criteria, as key to solving the puzzle of impact we are so often accused to consciously avoid. Current focusing on metrics inevitably “loses” everything that has essential value in SSH, making the measurement of the performance of these disciplines “obsolete” or irrelevant to society. Thus, the quantification of research results is not only inappropriate as a method, but also produces social consequences — both for SSH and for society itself, to which it denies the results of our work. Hence, it is also socially harmful.

However, our impact on society is considered outdated because the type of knowledge we produce has lost the appeal of social significance. If we turn to global changes in the perception of our disciplines by knowledge-driven institutions and organizations, we can see that in the latest version of advocating the importance of SSH for society — especially the humanities — their instrumental role stands out. During recent decades, significant progress has been made in the way in which academic policy, and related policies of peace and development, are perceived by the social sciences and humanities. In that regard, what we can, and I think should, do is to join UNESCO’s great peacetime project and those of other key international organizations, which at the same time will enable us to achieve the professional and social goals of our disciplines.

Concluding Recommendation

- As much as possible, assist in eliminating heritage from daily politics. Rather than filling in the gaps in news on political parties and state officials, heritage should be returned to research, education and cultural institutions.
- Rekindle interest in and financing for humanities and social sciences. Rethink consequentially the research funding and evaluation framework currently predominant in the region, but also globally, which is based on scientometrics/assessment of cosmopolitan academic reputation of scholars and institutions rather than analysis of their true social impact and historically affirmed cultural role within communities affected by policy work. It humiliates, alienates, and turns most local scholars against development goals. In addition to that, it reactively brings them back to a mode of operation that is closest to the discourse of interpretative sovereignty and methodological nationalism
- Local knowledge, research, institutions, and experts should all be respected and not sidelined as is often the case. It is prudent to approach local academics with humility, as their continued marginalization, both in policy-work and in academia, reinforces social exclusion and prevents achieving development goals in the broadest population. As a result, some of them develop fundamentalist beliefs and provide intellectual infrastructure for extremism. They should be regarded as important “missing stakeholders” whose integration should be prioritized within stabilization agenda.
- Respect for local academic and cultural institutions serves the building of a policy continuum. Since the population has a high level of trust in humanities scholarship all over the region, these disciplines have not yet suffered the harmful repercussions of global trends such as science denialism and crisis of public trust in expert knowledge. Where stakeholder involvement is a main aim, such as in identity management policies, humanities experts from

fields such as history, history of art, archeology, ethnology, folklore and alike provide the most useful bridge builders.

- In terms of intangible heritage as a tool for reconciliation and peacekeeping in post-conflict regions, the Western Balkans provides a clear and instructive example of the right impacts of conferring safeguarding to ethnologists. This might serve as a model for shifting sensitive identity-based concerns from the public to formalized methods of heritage management by experts working as civil servants employees in other parts of the world. Consider extending the bureaucratization of identity-related issues in your region as well, since the Western Balkans case demonstrates promising prospects.
- The projected negative repercussions of state-managed heritage protection, such as intentional exclusion of minority heritage, have been demonstrated to be less prevalent when ethnologist and other humanities scholars steer the process than in identity management schemes administered directly by ministries and other political actors under constant public pressure. At the same time, keep an eye out for additional negative steering effects and remedy them along the road, working closely not just with governments but also with learned societies, universities, institutes and prominent minority NGOs.
- The post-conflict reconciliation potential of ICH safeguarding should be modified so it does not challenge persistent primordial loyalties while simultaneously introducing the goals of the international development instruments. Bearers of ethnic identity politics should instead be incentivized and trained as bearers of ICH who safeguard and promote it through common and unified practices (not as rivals who compete for the honor of being the only ones on some list). Activities aimed at integration of three key conventions should be fostered and the link between the Operational Directives and the Faro convention pursued, as it promises most in that regard.
- If you strive for peace and reconciliation based on cultural policies, serial (multi-state) nominations, promoted by UNESCO, have to be submitted. Communities who share-while-contesting heritage elements have to be brought together by a novel structure of regional ICH safeguarding management proposed on the basis of the results of this research.

Special emphasis is given here to possible ways ICH safeguarding networks throughout the Western Balkans could be remodeled.^{xviii} This includes the introduction of regional and multistate inclusive registers that would encompass elements of dissonant, shared, difficult or even dark heritage. For this to work, it is not necessary to harmonize (a) safeguarding networks and (b) ethnological-anthropological curricula in the Western Balkan countries, as this proved undesirable among colleagues/interlocutors. Instead, it should be accompanied by a change in the framework of evaluation of social sciences and humanities that would be modeled to recognize SSH themselves as heritage.

It is in this triangle of a) contextual tuning of heritage safeguarding towards peace, reconciliation and development, b) enhanced research and teaching on collective identities, and c) fair and relevant evaluation of SSH, that solutions for other post-conflict regions should be sought.

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ⁱⁱ The fieldwork activities in the Western Balkans, and the knowledge-to-policy aspects of this research, were funded through the Civil Society Scholar Award 2019 by the Open Society Foundation “Towards Inclusive Intangible

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- iii. Bechev, D., F. Ejdus and D. Taleski., 2015. Culture of Regional Cooperation in Southeast Europe. Balkans in Europe Policy Advisory Group (Biepag). Belgrade: European Fund for the Balkans, p. 8 <https://Biepag.Eu/Wp-Content/Uploads/2021/07/BIEPAG-Culture-of-Regional-Cooperation-in-the-Western-Balkans.pdf>
 - iv. <https://en.unesco.org/creativity/policy-monitoring-platform/council-ministers-culture-south>
 - v. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/see>
 - vi. <https://www.rcc.int/home>.
 - vii. <http://comocosee.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Belgrade-Declaration-2011.pdf>, http://comocosee.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Ohrid-Declaration_final-2006.pdf.
 - viii. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/ljubljana-process>. The Ljubljana Process explicitly stressed the value of heritage for development, as a platform that seeks to present identity and culture as inextricably tied to stability and prosperity, which is in fact important for putting humanities and social sciences back on the map of research and development policymakers via culture and heritage. <https://book.coe.int/en/cultural-heritage/6144-heritage-for-development-in-south-east-europe.html>
 - ix. The phenomenon of “culturalization” of EU accession criteria for the EU candidate countries is mostly centered on issues related to perceived or truly existing lack of safeguarding of cultural heritage belonging to minorities and is a pressing political issue in the WB region for more than a decade. (Milenković and Milenković 2013a)
 - x. <https://ich.unesco.org/en/directives>.
 - xi. <https://en.unesco.org/fieldoffice/venice/ichsee>.
 - xii. The analysis of social consequences accompanied by specific recommendations for fine tuning the existing system of research assessment in Serbia and the Western Balkans and the strategy for its considerable change have been outlined recently as well: Milenkovic, M., 2020. *‘In the Name Of’ Europe: On the Counterindications of Social Science and Humanities Research Assessment Criteria (in Serbia)*. Belgrade: Faculty of Philosophy and Dosije studio.
 - xiii. <https://ich.unesco.org/en/directives>; <https://ich.unesco.org/doc/src/32121-EN.pdf>
 - xiv. <http://rm.coe.int/16806f6a03>
 - xv. <https://www.osce.org/mc/40881?download=true>; <https://www.osce.org/odihr/elections/14304?download=true>
 - xvi. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/410391468333060344/Conflict-and-reconstruction-roles-for-the-World-Bank>; <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/743151530217186766/ESF-Guidance-Note-8-Cultural-Heritage-English.pdf>
 - xvii. Milenković, M. [Marko], 2022. Trajectories of differentiated EU integration for the Western Balkans. In: B. Leruth, S. Gänzle and J. Trondal, eds. *The Routledge Handbook of Differentiation in the European Union*. London: Routledge, 551-564.
 - xviii. The CoMoSEE should consider modification of its organizational structure and involve both academics and practitioners devoted to identity-related issues most at risk. The inclusion of academic anthropologists and researchers from related disciplines in ICH should be considered a global standard. Ethnology-anthropology continuum, as detected in the Western Balkans, could be comparatively used with that goal.